

THREE YEARS AFTER DISPLACEMENT: THE EVERYDAY LIVES OF UKRAINE'S IDPs

BRIEF PAPER PRELIMINARY RESEARCH RESULTS

After more than three years of conflict, over 1.5 million internally displaced people are still facing issues with housing, health care, employment and, most importantly, having to return to war-torn territories.

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Ukraine's hidden tragedy: Understanding the outcomes of population displacement from the country's war-torn regions

About the project

This interdisciplinary project explores the experiences of Ukrainians displaced by Russia's annexation of Crimea and the de facto invasion of its eastern regions, through the use of intersectional and interdisciplinary approaches. The project uses qualitative methodologies including, in-depth and semi-structural interviews with IDPs and representatives of NGOs, international organizations, central and local authorities in several Lviv, Kyiv, Chernihiv, Kharkiv, Dnipro, Zaporizhzhia and Mariupol regions. It also includes collaboration with the Ukrainian Catholic University (Professor Oksana Mikheieva), the NGOs Dobrochyn, Chernihiv Centre for Human rights and the Platform for Cultural Initiatives IZOLYATSIA. The empirical work for this project was conducted in 2017, allowing it to reflect on changes on situation of IDPs after three years of conflict, and also to evaluate the social consequences of recent changes in legislation regarding displaced people in Ukraine.

In this progress report, we focus on the most urgent issues internally displaced persons raised during meetings and interviews: housing, health care, registration and pensions.

To date 89 interviews, of the expected 115, have been undertaken, providing the preliminary results for discussion here. The full report is expected in March 2018 and will be published on the project's website, www.idpukraine.com, and on our pages hosted by the University of Birmingham, and also will be reflected in papers in academic journals.

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Housing

‘YOU CANNOT INTEGRATE INTO SOCIETY WITHOUT HOUSING’

The lack of affordable and adequate housing is the number one issue for internally displaced people:

- Most IDPs live in rented apartments. The living conditions in many cases are not appropriate considering the size of families and/or special needs
- To rent an apartment is very difficult because owners often do not want to rent to IDPs (prejudiced that they cannot pay in time). If they are willing they often increase the price for IDPs. In some towns, the rental market became very tight because of the number of IDPs
- The market of apartments for rent is mostly informal in Ukraine which make most IDPs vulnerable (short notice for requirement to move out, increasing payments etc)
- There are no regional differences in accessible housing, but social and economic differences – income and size of a family, job. The high prices for accommodation in Kyiv stop many IDPs from moving there.
- Dormitories provided by the state for IDPs were not able to accommodate everyone in need. Furthermore some IDPs have been asked to leave, some increase their prices and some are still under construction. The new dormitory in Kirovohrad oblast does not have many IDPs because of undesirable location (remote and little nearby work).
- The IDPs social benefit is not enough to pay for the rent.
- The situation with housing stops elderly people to move from Non-government controlled areas.
- The necessity to pay for the rent, difficulties of employment force many families to move back to NGCA.

‘You cannot integrate into society without housing. You always live with suitcases. So, we keep everything what we do not use in boxes and then it is easier to move and find another accommodation. Owners always look and if they feel you have stability they put the price of the rent up. You always with suitcases and always have to think what to do tomorrow. Which plans could you make? Nothing really is you do not have any stability. When you are young you can live in rented flats. But when you are elderly, and touchwood will get sick – which landlord would keep you in a flat? It is very frustrating’.
(Female, 58 years old, from Luhansk oblast, lives in Kharkiv)

CASE STUDY: DORMITORY IN TOWN CHUHUYEV KHARKIV OBLAST

In 2014 some rooms in a building which was used for different offices, were transformed as a temporal dormitory. By efforts of volunteers and internally displaced people new windows, toilets and showers were installed in a building. Since 2014 this temporal housing has received over 300 people. Currently seventeen people live here: elderly, single mothers, people with disabilities. They pay only utility bills and live in very difficult conditions because cannot afford a better housing. But now the Chuhuyev administration sues IDPs and demand them to leave.

'From our IDPs benefits we pay for utilities, and use our pension to buy some food. (...) There are 8 people in our room. There is a woman born in 1937, another woman is 50 years old, another one is 57, one girl is 33 years old, she had several surgeries in Kharkiv and Kyiv, and she need more as she has shrapnel wounds. In another room, there are people with kids, men and women. We live like in a train station. Somebody wants to have a rest, somebody wants some joy, children run around, but it is a dormitory. The inconvenience is that there are too many of us here. Now it is not too many but there used to be about 200 people. It is impossible – a queue to the toilet and shower. Can you imagine that? Only 2 toilets and one shower for 200 people? That is all. How is that possible? (female, 77 years old, from Alcheevsk, lives in Chuhuevo Kharkiv oblast, moved in 2015)

'We were offered to move to different city – to Sumy or Kryvyi Rih, I do not remember now. But we are not stray musicians, rights? We are temporally displaced people. When the war will be finished we will go back home. How could we intermediate them if we live in that 2 rooms where they placed us? I do not know. Where could I go to another city? Children go to kindergarten. Lena – to kindergarten, Irina – to school, Anna - to college. Olga – in spite the fact that she has disability, has a bronchial asthma, she went to work to the factory informally. What to do? I would like to work but I cannot physically, I have such a rear disease, one for a million people... I have to stop after each 20 metres walking.' (female, 50 years old, from Alcheevsk, lives in Chuhuevo Kharkiv oblast, names have been changed)

HOUSING VERSUS INADEQUATE LOCAL MANAGEMENT

There would be less cases when people have go back to NGCA and feel more integrated in Government Controlled Areas of Ukraine if authorities and contractors would more effectively manage the housing resources. Several projects were started with a big delay – for example, in Kramatoroks, Bakhmut, Slobyansk and Novhorodka,

The EU funded project on apartments building for 84 IDPs families is still not ready in Kramatorsk which started in 2015 is not finished yet. It worth 1.8 mln Euro from the EU, 200K Euro from the local budget (DepoDonbas 14/06/2017)

In Bakhmut city, all 16 apartments which planned for IDPs were distributed solely among the families of army personnel serving in the military

The Slovyansk City Council launched an EU funded project “Housing for Internally Displaced Persons” in April 2015 but started the construction only in 2017 (see Social housing... 2017)

The dormitory for IDPs in Novhorodka Kirovohrad oblast (EU funds) has been opened only in summer 2017. Because of delays and also remoteness of the town, lack of jobs and infrastructure (the town located 40 km far from Kirovohrad) only 32 people instead of a planned 450 live there (TSN.ua 10/10/2017)

ARE ANY PROSPECTS FOR AFFORDABLE HOUSING?

IDPs are not among the categories of population entitled for social housing in Ukraine. There is only one exception regarding local initiatives under the application of the Laws “On Local Self-Government in Ukraine” and “On Housing Fund for Social Purposes”. The legislative amendments of April 2017 allows for IDPs to receive subsidized mortgages for the construction or purchase of housing (50 percent of the cost could be subsidized by the state) and the bank interest is 7 percent. However, it more reserved for residents of local communities who live in inappropriate conditions, and the required deposit is too high for most of IDPs.

In 2017 there is only UAN 30 ml (approximately £840,000) in the budget for the State program ‘Affordable housing’ (which could provide housing for a maximum 70-80 families). Most of the program has to be financed via local budgets. Also, IDPs had to present the documents from NGCA that they do not have housing there. This requirement was removed after activists organized a ten day flash mob protest near the Rada in September 2017.

Photo from the flesh mob of IDPs near Verkhovna Rada, Kyiv in September 2017
<https://donbass.comments.ua/news/132270-pereselentsi-zrya-ustroili-party.html>

Ukrainian politicians are not currently considering any change in existing policy towards affordable housing for IDPs. As first deputy Minister for temporarily occupied territories and internally displaced persons of Ukraine Yusuf Kurkchi mentioned, 'This problem [the provision of IDPs with housing], among other things, is one of the most expensive for the state, because at current prices on the primary and secondary markets the cost of this problem is now almost unrealistic for the state. The issue concerns about \$20-40 billion' (UkrInform 08/08/2017). Another deputy Minister, Georgy Tuka, pointed out on preferential credits for purchase of housing: 'The most prospective from the financial point of you is preferential credit for the purchase of housing. Like it we or now, but 99 per cent of our foreign partners, and I understand them, absolutely against to give social housing into ownership' (Vchasnoua.com 22/09/2017).

According to our interviews, current opportunities are not affordable even for families where both spouses work as the price of deposit and a mortgage is too high. Also, those who work in informal sector of economy, which is very common in Ukraine and often not through choice, cannot even apply for preferential credit.

The announcement in early 2017 of a draft law which would allow to IDPs who have property in NGCA to give it to the state and receive a right for a free housing in CGA, and those who do not have a property, have a social housing in CGA for 5 years, is still not approved.

'The housing always was a problem, but when you move and have to start everything from the beginning, working days and nights, it is unreal to buy even a small flat. I try to do something for two years, we both work hard, but cannot imagine how to buy housing. And we cannot sell anything there. What about an option if the bank or a state could buy a property which people left in NGCA? (...) Let's say if a flat used to cost 30k US dollars before the war, now it worth 15k, it could be much easier for people to have a deposit for a mortgage'. (female, from Donetsk, used to have a big house, lives with a husband and 3 children)

As a result, **elderly people and other vulnerable groups** are the most excluded from the current emerging opportunities for housing, and are still in risk of returning to NGCA or to deeper socio-economic marginalization.

‘A BIRD IN THE HAND IS BETTER THAN TWO IN THE BUSH’: WHY PEOPLE MOVE BACK TO NGCA

According to the recent survey of 4290 people crossing the ‘line of contact’, conducted by the Rights for Protection in June-July, in the five operating EECPs located in Donetsk (EECPs Maiorske, Marinka, Hnutove and Novotroitske) and Luhansk (Stanytsia Luhanska) Oblasts 46.2 percent of them moved to the Government controlled territories but then returned (Right for Protection June-July 2017). For about half of them the high rent was main factor to take this decision, and 32 percent mentioned ‘other reasons’, 29.4 – stabilized situation, 17.6 – work and 0.7 – negative attitudes in host community.

Interviews taken with IDPs during our research showed that the housing issues are one the most crucial factors when they think about their prospects of living in GCA. Even when the family copes with a high price for rent, they still cannot afford the mortgage and consider going back. Also, the impossibility in many case bring elderly parents (again – housing issues in many cases), make the choice to go back to so called self-proclaimed republics as not a desirable one but unavoidable. Therefore, the percentage of those who go back because of housing in reality is higher because ‘other’ reasons include all this complex spectrum of issues around place of living and caring responsibilities.

‘Ukraine calls – come here! But what do we have in reality – could really my retired parents move here? You should have money to move, and money to live, and they will not be living in a rented accommodation, they are elderly. Also, my father has two greenhouses and grow vegetables. A bird in the hand is better than two in the bush. My parents would love to move. But where they could move?! This is the first question. They want to come to us and buy a cheap house in a village. But I have not settled here yet, as if I will have to move to another city? And secondly, if they move, we have to buy furniture etc because they cannot take anything from there.’ (Male, 44 years old, from Mariupol, lives in near Kyiv)

Access to health care. Disabilities. Mental health

The access to health care is hugely problematic all over all Ukraine. Due to the deficit of resources and low wages of staff, informal payments are embedded in all levels of medical help (see Stepurko et al 2015, Williams et al 2013 etc). Also, very often people have to buy medication when they are in hospitals as well.

For forced displaced people the situation is aggravated by the fact that health services in NGCA are 'running out of essential medicines and facing serious shortage of doctors' (Holt 2015). A lot of them are facing life threaten conditions before arriving to GCA and need the urgent support. However, most all of respondents in our study who had to apply for the medical support found it very difficult – starting with the necessity of having the document of IDPs, requirements to give informal or formal payments and in some cases even hate speech.

All informants in our research had to pay for medicines while being in hospitals and for an x-ray films. One fifth of those who addressed medical help faced difficulties that they have not been registered in that medical centres or was not able to provide the document of IDP.

CIVILIANS WITH WAR INJURIES: NO STATE RESPONSE

Informants with war injures pointed at **the necessity to treat civilians who received injuries as a result of armed conflict as war veterans**. Currently they rely only on treatment which is paid by charitable foundations and international organization and do not receive a special pension or other compensations.

Case 1. Man from Debaltsevo, 36 years old, now lives in Kharkiv with a wife and 2 children. He was injured by a mine escaping from the NGCA and was able to find a charity which paid for his surgeries in a private clinic in Kyiv. Then he received the disability status 2 group which allows to receive social benefits and not work. He used to have a salary of UAN6000 before the war and now receives almost 3 times less. He wants to work but there is no accessible transport and buildings, and not many jobs to work from home. His wife has to work hard and take children to school and back, and also to look after him.

Case 2. Civilian man had shrapnel wound in his head, and due to help of family and volunteers was able to escape from the front line. The family have not received anything from the state except of benefits. The hospital even refused to take him without the document of IDP. This document had to be issued only with his presence, so he had to be in a queue with 200 people. The hospital did not provide necessary high technological surgery. Due to Caritas, Red Cross, Canadian embassy and charitable organizations he had received surgeries in Prague and Kyiv. After two years he cannot eat, cannot serve himself, wife has to work, look after him, after kids, pay for a rent of flat.

‘The only help we received is from charities. And clothes, medication... Our authorities, instead – nothing, everywhere we addressed, just impossible. But he is a victim, but for what? He is civilian. He was at home. But there should be some support from the state, a status. (...) The last time he had a surgery – Canadian mission paid for his surgery and medication, but we had to pay to the public hospital for every day. So, Canada helps us, but our own state does not. But what about people who does not have a family support? I know a woman from Kramatorsk, she lost both her legs, 50 percent of her body has burns. She has a small son and nobody else, and they have to survive from her pension as disable person.’ (wife of a man who was injured, 37 years old, from Debaltsevo, lives in Kharkiv)

DISABILITIES AND BORDERS

About 4 percent of registered IDPs have disabilities - 66,434 persons in 2016. According to UNHCR, the access to disabilities benefits, lack of accessible and affordable transport are the main issues faced by persons with disabilities among IDPs (UNHCR October 2016). Our research also revealed the discrimination at the job market, the lack of reliable jobs which could be done from home.

People with disabilities who live in NGCA have to cross the contact line to access pensions, but often in case if they are not mobile or nobody could help they alienated from their benefits. Those who moved to GCA face difficulties to prolong their disability status because of the long bureaucratic process. A lot of families have to live ‘between’ have to provide assistance to those who have to stay in NGCA.

‘My father [lives in NGCA] was injured in a coal mine in 2001, he barely survived and received disabled status. But then he was not able to prolong it in Ukraine as he was due three years ago before the war [in Ukraine people with disabilities has to re-registered their status regularly]. Then we tried to do it in Kyiv but they do not have an expertise in coal mine injuries. (...) My grandma has chronical diseases. It’s very difficult, father has to go to Mariupol to buy a medicine for her because it is 3 times more expensive there. Her condition became worse all the time as there are no qualified doctors.’ (male, 27 years old, lives in Kyiv, from Donetsk)

MENTAL HEALTH

About one third of IDPs experience various forms of mental health issues, but only a 26 per cent have applied for a professional help (survey of 2000 IDPs, see Roberts at al 2017). This current project, and also initial research on ‘Mental health and well-being of internally displaced people: coping tactics and resilience in conflict-affected societies’

(Wellcome Trust funded, Kuznetsova, Catling and Round), also confirmed that even when experiencing anxiety and PTS symptoms most of informants do not apply for a professional help. Very often it is connected with existing prejudices and stigma regarding mental health in Ukraine in general. Also, there is a lack of free services, lack of professionals who can work with people suffered from war. General practitioners are not trained to provide the mental health consultations and treatment. Importantly, precariat conditions of many IDPs and the necessity of coping with everyday issues, lack of resources and time are main barriers for applying for mental health support.

'Specialists [psychologists] cried. As soon as I began to talking to them they starting to cry and ask 'just stop it'. I say, well, maybe you have to be fired and somebody else could help then?' (laughing) (Male, 36 years old, from Debaltsevo, 36 years old, now lives in Kharkiv, has a severe injury from war and his mother was killed)

'When we just arrived, we addressed to psychotherapist. We had some medicine. Because this endless anxiety we did not sleep at all. And then we started to sleep, but then it became worse, and all three of us [she, her husband and son] had medicine. We took it but our son still has anxiety and does not sleep well at all. There is not stability at all, it is all uncertain. Also, no people with whom you can just talk and share some memories. It is just an age and difficult to make new friends.' (Female, 58 years old, from Luhansk oblast, lives in Kharkiv)

As a result, alternative coping tactics are common including escapist behaviours but social activism as well e.g. – volunteering, religious communities' involvement (especially among groups of support were named (Evangelists, Adventists, Catholics).

Registration, documentation and monthly assistance

Slava Bo. Tryptic 'Displaced' / (Parts of headline, nails and a damaged passport) From the exposition during the launching a virtual platform Luhansk. Arts & Facts, Kiyv, November 2016. Photo: Irina Kuznetsova

The research revealed very long procedures and queues for registration and documentation in eastern and south-eastern parts of Ukraine. This prevents some

people from registering as IDPs, and also stop others receiving their benefits in time. The decree N 689 from 13/09/2017 includes changes for procedures of checks and verifications of IDPs for social benefits. Checks of the place of residency will be cancelled for the following categories of IDPs: who work in authorities, militants, IDPs who verified their identity in Oschadbank. Also, Social benefits for people with disabilities of 1 group or needs a constant care can receive cash at home via post.

'From the state only 2400 (UAN per month for all family, approximately £67) but with difficulty, because I did not have any documents. I had to wait over a month for a passport. Firstly I applied in Slyavyansk, but received nothing. Then moved to Kharkiv, and received our passports here. it was difficult, just as a black hole. ... We have to do it via lawyers, and asked people who work for the emergency situations organization, for everything, not to overthrow a president, but just to receive our passports.' (male, 36 years old, from Debaltsevo, now lives in Kharkiv, cannot work as was injured by mine when leaving the war zone)

In some case people refuse to register as an internally displaced because of ideological reasons, to escape the hassle of obtaining documents, to avoid the military service, and also some people without documents including some Roma.

'Anyway, as a person who is Ukrainian, why do I need to register?! I have a passport stating that I am Ukrainian citizen. Why do I need to have a separate registration?! (...) The state just wants to think that if I am IDP that I am homeless' (...) I am not going to live with a document of an IDP. I want to live free' (male, 42, Lviv, from Donetsk).

'How can we call this 400 Hrivna support (£11)? For this we have to degrade ourselves and go to all these institutions. We made some attempts but to have to go every half year and tell where do you work, it is not worth it. And now we do not receive any financial support absolutely, in spite the fact that legally and constitutionally we should.' (male, 27 years old, Kyiv, from Donetsk)

The **monthly targeted assistance to IDPs** started from October 01, 2014 (Resolution No. 505) and consist of UAH 442 for working displaced persons, UAH 884 for pensioners and children UAH 1,130 for disabled persons (from December 01 - UAH 1,247).

It is not provided if any of the IDP's family members owns a residential property located in regions other than the temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine, areas of counter-terrorist operations and settlements located on the line of contact; and/or if any of the IDP's family members have an amount on deposit exceeding 10-times (from 2017 – 25-times) the size of the minimum cost of living as set for working persons.

The minimum cost of living in Ukraine in 2017 is UAN 1624 which is not enough even for food, but even though the representatives of authorities and mass-media often blame IDPs for receiving this monthly targeted assistance, calling them 'pension tourists' and

'social tourists' and suspect over a half million persons for not-moving to GCA but registered as IDP.

All informants of our research indicated that their pensions and social benefits were suspended for several months, even for those who never left CGA. Once per year IDPs benefits were reported being delayed for 2 months. Those who was not able to find an official job within first few months cannot receive benefits (50 percent of working informants).

The checks of places of residence is disturbing everyday life of IDPs, their employment and also created misunderstandings and paperwork mistakes.

'Now it seems a bit better and I can to prolong my IDP document within a day. But then they said: we will be checking, you have to sit at home. But it is very inconvenient, if they call and say you must be at home for 3 days. For example, I am very pleased when I was asked to distribute leaflets, it is some income for me. I ask if I can come to social services by myself, and they say – 'no, you cannot – maybe you lie, and you go to Donetsk area.' This is very hard. It means they do not believe us. They think that we travel backwards and forwards'. (female, 71 years old, from Horlovka, lives in Kharkiv)

Some IDPs faced with corruption and inefficiency of social services: *'I had problems. They [social services] said that they lost a folder with my documents. Of course, because I have to receive 1600 for a child, plus 2400 as a mother of several children, so 4000 overall. Why to pay me? It is better to throw my folder via the window. Always corruption. I have realised that they simply hidden my folder by purpose. And there are many cases like that. It calls corruption.'* (female, focus group in Chernihiv)

Pensions

Ukrainian citizens from NGCA have to register as IDPs in order to receive pensions and social benefits (for disability for example). Authorities verifies IDPs place of residency in GCA every 6 months.

'The number of persons from the NGCA receiving pensions dropped dramatically from 956,000 in January 2016 to 391,000 in April 2017, due to ongoing verifications. This represents only 30 per cent of pensioners who were residing in the NGCA in August 2014. More than **500,000** Ukrainians lost their pensions since January 2016.' (UNHCR August 2017)

The draft law no. 6692 was elaborated by Rights for Protection, Donbas SOS, UNHCR and other international and local organizations and MPs and was registered on 12/07/2017. It aims to **de-link pension payments from IDP status**, ensuring the right to a pension irrespective of the place of residence; reduce verification procedures and

cancel the restrictions on possibility of receiving an unclaimed pension only for three years for this category of persons.

The stigma of 'pension-' and 'social benefits' tourists creates the negative image of displaced people and those who live in NGCSA and discourage the processes of social cohesion and reconciliation.

PENSIONS FOR IDPS FROM CRIMEA: LEGAL QUIZ AND VIOLATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS

The pensions for IDPs from Crimea reveal the lack of mechanism of legal procedures and numerous violation of personal information and human rights.

As Anna Rossomakhina, advocate of Helsinki group for Human Rights mentioned in interview, 'Nowadays the pension fund of Russia has personal data of all pensioners who became IDPs in Ukraine. They have all database, several thousand people'. The process of receiving pension documents from Crimea takes from several months for a year as it goes via Moscow or Krasnodar.

Case: 'In our practice, one woman with her relatives left Crimea in 2014. She had a severe cancer. She died in April 2016. Before that she was in a bed for one and a half years. After her death we requested her pension documents, they arrived and it was said that the pension was paid till August 2016 in Crimea. And they said to relatives that they do not have any rights as all pension was paid'.

Recommendations

In our research, we asked participants to provide recommendations for authorities and NGOs for improving of conditions of internally displaced people. Here is a list of the most common suggestions:

Housing:

- Provide free housing, even if only for the first few years
- Consider the use a property left in NGCA as a deposit for a mortgage
- Simplify a procedure of subsidizing utility bills (now you have to have an official contract and temporal registration by the owner)
- Provide social housing for those who with disabilities or elderly people who need assistance

Social life:

- Create social maps for every city which will help for IDPs to navigate their life there

Children:

- Provide assistance for children for summer holidays (camps, health farms etc)

People with war injures:

- To give a status of war veterans to civilians who were injured because of war

Entrepreneurs:

- Provide manuals and legal advice for private entrepreneurs who registered in NGCA
- Special programs for business in 200 km zone

Registration and documentation:

- Simplify the registration – to cancel the necessity to register every half year
- Create a mobile brigades for registration for elderly and people with disabilities
- To increase the number of staff in municipal social services
- Provide manuals with new information regarding the procedures of benefits and documentation for IDPs

As the OCHA report states it is necessary to 'recognize in all actions that IDPs, regardless of whether they live in NGCA and GCA, as citizens or part of the regular population of Ukraine with the same rights as non-displaced Ukrainians, but victims of

conflict, and have specific needs and vulnerabilities' (Breaking the Impasse. OCHA 2017).

The delay in the improvement of living conditions and law enforcement for many of IDPs simply means the inevitability of a return to territories where the continual violation of human rights and insecurity threaten their lives.

References

Crossing the line of contact monitoring report. June-July 2017. The Right to Protection http://vpl.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Crossing-the-line-of-contact_1.pdf

DepoDonbas 14/06/2017 <https://dn.depo.ua/rus/kramatorsk/kramatorsk/dovgobud-dlya-pereselenciv-20170613587963>

Vchasnoua.com 22/09/2017 <https://vchasnoua.com/donbass/53149-99-zapadnykh-partnerov-protiv-peredachi-sotsialnogo-zhilya-v-sobstvennost-pereselentsam-georgij-tuka>

UkrInform 08/08/2017 <https://www.ukrinform.net/rubric-economy/2281878-housing-for-all-idps-would-cost-ukraine-2040-bln-ministry.html>

TSN.ua 10/10/2017 <https://ru.tsn.ua/ukrayina/na-kirovogradschine-pustuet-obschezhitie-dlya-pereselencev-iz-zony-ato-i-kryma-1009795.html>

UNHCR October 2016. Ukraine. Refugees and internally displaced people with disabilities.

<http://unhcr.org.ua/attachments/article/317/UNHCR%20UKRAINE%20Disabilities%20Update%20OCT16%20FINAL.pdf>

UNHCR Protection monitoring update. Ukraine 1-31 August 2017.

<http://unhcr.org.ua/attachments/article/317/2017%2008%20UNHCR%20UKRAINE%20Protection%20Monitoring%20update%20FINAL%20EN.pdf>

Roberts, B., Makhshvili, N., Javakhishvili, J., Karachevskyy, A., Kharchenko, N., Shpiker, M., & Richardson, E. (2017). Mental health care utilisation among internally displaced persons in Ukraine: results from a nation-wide survey. *Epidemiology and psychiatric sciences*, 1-12.

Social housing solutions for internally displaced and conflict-affected population: comparative analysis of Bakhmut, Slovyansk and Kramatorsk projects. Norwegian Refugee Council. 2017 https://www.nrc.no/globalassets/pdf/briefing-notes/ukraine/case-study-on-social-housing-for-idps_eng.pdf

Stepurko, T., Pavlova, M., Gryga, I., & Groot, W. (2015). Making patients pay: informal patient payments in Central and Eastern European countries. *Frontiers in public health*, 3.

UNHCR March 2017. Ukraine. Key messages on internal displacement.

<http://unhcr.org.ua/attachments/updates/2017%2003%20UNHCR%20UKRAINE%20Key%20Messages%20Briefing%20Note%20FINAL%20EN.pdf>

Williams, C. C., Round, J., & Rodgers, P. (2013). The role of informal economies in the post-Soviet world: The end of transition?. Routledge.

Breaking the Impasse. Reducing Protracted internal displacement as a collective outcome. Case Studye Ukraine. OCHA

https://www.humanitarianresponse.info/system/files/documents/files/breaking_the_impasse_case_study_ukraine_en.pdf

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